

Timbira (Canela)

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Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

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Entry tags: South American Religions, Religious Group

The Timbira are located in eastern South America and are comprised of about 15 tribes. This entry focuses on the Canela group living in Brazil (mainly in the state of Maranhão) around the time of 1915, prior to the reservation era beginning in the 1960's. The name "Canela" includes the three adjacent but independent Timbira groups of Kénkatéye, Apã'nyekra, and Rãmkö'kamekra. The term Canela was originally used by settlers, and translates to cinnamon or shinbone in Portuguese; "Canela" is the modern term. Traditionally, the Canela lived in a large, circular village plan with houses all facing a central plaza. These villages historically contained up to 1,500 individuals, but the introduction of diseases in the 1800 has dramatically reduced the population (Crooker and Beierle, 2012). At the time this entry focuses on, the largest Canela group (the Rãmkö'kamekra) was comprised of about 230 people. Canela social units include the individual family, matrilineal extended family, matrilineal exogamous moieties (each includes half of the village), nonexogamous rainy season moieties, plaza groups, plaza moieties, age classes, age-class moieties, and six men's societies. Note that these groupings are all within the village level. The village is led by a chief (pa'hi) and a group of councilmen. Pa'hi have minimal political control and serve primarily as peacemaker and ceremonial leaders. Ceremonies are important, but not necessarily religious in nature and are largely associated with the social and economic importance surrounding puberty rites and the calendrical cycle. Religion and beliefs about the supernatural do not play a significant role in Canela daily life. Supernatural beings (such as the sun and moon) and ghosts are present, but not described in substantial ethnographic details. Religious practitioners, referred to as medicine men or shamans, consult with spirits to cure illness and sometimes gain a "disease substance" that can be used to afflict others. Religion does not exist within a distinct sphere of life for the Canela; this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1900 CE - 1936 CE

Region: Canela territory, Brazil, ca. 1915

Region tags: South America, Brazil

Canela territory, Brazil, ca. 1915

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

– Source 3: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.

– Source 1: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=so08-001>

– Source 1 Description: Nimuendaju, Curt, and Robert Harry Lowie. 1946. "Eastern Timbira." University Of California Publications In American Archaeology And Ethnology. Berkeley And Los Angeles: Universtiy of California Press.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=so08-000>

– Source 2 Description: Crocker, William H. (William Henry), and John Beierle. 2012. "Culture Summary: Canela." New Haven: Human Relations Area Files.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "The Capuchin missionaries of Barra do Corda have never spent more than a few hours as transients among the Canella tribes, whose children they would baptize on such occasions, once in a while also marrying a couple. Between 1896 and 1901 they had three or four Rąmkō'kamekra boys in their school in Barra do Corda; one of them is still living and shows no trace of their instruction. Pompeu Sobrinho erroneously reports that the Canella were once settled at the missions of Grajahú and Barra do Corda" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:241). "The Rąmkō'kamekra and Apą'nyekra have hitherto had neither Catholic nor Protestant missionaries. Such knowledge as they have of Christianity results from observation of Neobrazilians and the occasional, clumsy efforts of these neighbors to impose their ideas. However, the possibility of adopting the alien faith is quite inconceivable to these Indians, in whose life even indigenous religious notions play a subordinate part. Accordingly, their supernaturalism has remained free of foreign admixture" (ibid, pg.242).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), indicates that internal warfare seems to be absent or rare (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), coded the Timbira as a 2.25, which is between 2 (external warfare seems to occur once every 3-10 years), and 3 (external warfare seems to occur at least once every two years). Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the Canela would actively proselytize and recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religion does not exist within a separate sphere of life for the Canela, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society. In this sense, the religion has political support.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Religious infrastructure is not present.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: There is no head of the religion. Religious practitioners such as medicine men or shamans are present, but there is no individual that serves as supreme leader. Further, a village chief (pa'hi) is present, but a group of councilmen rule the political realm of the village along with the pa'hi.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 494

Notes: According to Nimuendaju and Lowie (1946), at the time this entry focuses on there are 150 Kénkateye (pg.30), 118 Apa'nyekra (p.31), and 226 Rąmkō'kamekra (pg.33).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The Canela have many shamans—some who cure, and a few who also 'throw' illnesses. They do either activity through 'powers' received from the souls of the recently dead (me-karō, ghosts). Men (and rarely women) become shamans through carrying out specific instructions (mostly restrictions against 'pollutions') received during a series of visitations by ghosts, who first appear as animals" (Crocker and Beierle, 2012).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: A medicine-man consults with spirits to cure illnesses (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:239), and sometimes spirits give shaman "disease substance" which can be used to afflict others (pg.239). It appears that the terms "medicine-man" and "shaman" are used interchangeably by the principal ethnographer.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: "...a pupil had to abstain from meat pies and any other form of meat for at least a month; he must refrain from sex relations and daily rub his body with the small pieces of a yellow root in order to be visited by the spirits, who at last would appear to him in a dream. After announcing this result in the plaza he would be acknowledged as a shaman" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:239).

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: "...a pupil had to abstain from meat pies and any other form of meat for at least a month; he must refrain from sex relations and daily rub his body with the small pieces of a yellow root in order to be visited by the spirits, who at last would appear to him in a dream. After announcing this result in the plaza he would be acknowledged as a shaman" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:239).

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral

scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scripture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson, 1972 (Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson, 1972 (Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures), "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Every human being and every animal has a soul. Plants 'perhaps' also have a soul, but theirs plays no part. At death the soul leaves the body through the mouth; nobody knows how and where it enters the body. The soul of a dead person, the distinct shadow cast by him, and his image are all called mekarö" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:234).

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– I don't know

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "The spirits of the dead usually reside in village-like communities in the localities where they lived or were buried, that is, especially on old camp sites and in cemeteries, the will-o'-the-wisps occasionally rising from the ground of the latter being conceived as the spirits' camp fires. However, at times the souls also appear singly and in other places. Otherwise inexplicable shouting (mekapr̃ep), such as occasionally resounds at night in steppes and woods, is ascribed to roaming spirits. Another abode is below the water of the Lake Kukamóroča" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:234-235).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The spirits of the dead usually reside in village-like communities in the localities where they lived or were buried..." (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:234-235).

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

Notes: "The spirits of the dead usually reside in village-like communities in the localities where they lived or were buried..." (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:234-235).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: "The spirits of the dead usually reside in village-like communities in the localities where they lived or were buried..." (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:234-235).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details on burial practices.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The grave is more or less 2 meters in depth. Formerly it was round, and the corpse was put in there in a sitting posture, facing east. At present, at least among the R̄amkō'kamekra, the grave is exclusively rectangular, the corpse lying extended on its back" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:134).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– I don't know

Notes: It is unclear when burials switched from placing the corpse in a flexed position to placing the corpse in an extended position. "The grave is more or less 2 meters in depth. Formerly it was round, and the corpse was put in there in a sitting posture, facing east. At present, at least among the R̄amkō'kamekra, the grave is exclusively rectangular, the corpse lying extended on its back" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:134).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: "The grave is more or less 2 meters in depth. Formerly it was round, and the corpse was put in there in a sitting posture, facing east. At present, at least among the R̄amkō'kamekra, the grave is exclusively rectangular, the corpse lying extended on its back" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:134).

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that corpses would be exposed to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the practice of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: "Until some twenty years ago the Canella still maintained secondary burial in individual cases, at least for the hamrén; for the rest of the population the custom had fallen into desuetude. Formerly, the secondary interment took place three or five years after the first" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:135).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices in burials.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: "At least nowadays there are no funeral deposits except that a woman's carrying basket may be laid on her mound along with a gourd bowl, her spindle, and the like" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:134).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "The mats on which the corpse rests are folded over it and tied firmly at both ends and in the middle. Then the bundle is hung to a pole, which two men carry to the cemetery—at present from one and a half to two kilometers from the village. A few additional mats are taken along for the adjustment of the grave...The opening of the grave is covered with transversely laid pieces of wood, which are topped with mats before heaping up earth" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:134).

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "The mats on which the corpse rests are folded over it and tied firmly at both ends and in the middle. Then the bundle is hung to a pole, which two men carry to the cemetery—at present from one and a half to two kilometers from the village. A few additional mats are taken along for the adjustment of the grave...The opening of the grave is covered with transversely laid pieces of wood, which are topped with mats before heaping up earth" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:134).

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of family tomb-crypts.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: "Formerly, when secondary burial was still in vogue, the deceased was first buried

behind his mother's home, except for a *həmren* (p. 98). When I visited the *Krahō'* in 1930, these Indians seemed to have still maintained the custom of burial behind the house; the *Rəm̄kō'kamekra* of today would at most follow it in the case of an infant" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:134).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits as well as other non-human supernatural beings are present, but not described in extensive ethnographic detail. See questions below for available information.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic Atlas column 34, High Gods, indicates that "a high god [is] absent or not reported in substantial descriptions of religious beliefs" (Murdock, 1967).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The soul of a dead person, the distinct shadow cast by him, and his image are all called *mekarō* (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:234)." "Apart from some peculiarities due to their shadowy character, the souls lead an existence very similar to that of the living. They are neither more nor less happy" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:235).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Accompanying their living relatives, they [spirits of the deceased] protect them wherever possible, drive away poisonous snakes from their path, and appear to them in waking hours or dreams in order to warn them against misfortune. Normally they are invisible; but if they so desire they can turn visible even in the middle of the day, either in their mortal shape or in some beast's. At night their sudden appearance, as a rule of but momentary duration, strikes terror into the visionary's heart, so that he will remain ill for days—notwithstanding the fact that these spirits are not hostile to man" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:235).

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that human spirits are believed to have deliberate causal efficacy in the world.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Accompanying their living relatives, they [spirits of the deceased] protect them wherever possible, drive away poisonous snakes from their path, and appear to them in waking hours or dreams in order to warn them against misfortune" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:235).

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: "...the Canella believe that the shadow of a person who dies 'hungry,' that is, has not for some time prior to his demise taken any food, will return to his mother's home in search of sustenance" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:134).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The Sun and Moon are viewed as having deity-like qualities.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The purpose of all the general cult performances is to invoke the heavenly bodies [Sun and Moon] to protect food plants and animals. These acts comprise prayers to the Sun for rain (p. 62), for protection of game animals (p. 71), and on behalf of wild fruits (p. 72); and to the Moon to prosper the crops when maize has grown to about 3 feet in height (p. 62)" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:232).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

Notes: Previously human spirits as well as other non-human supernatural beings are present.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural monitoring.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural punishment.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of supernatural reward.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required partial sexual abstinence.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required sacrifice of time among the Canela.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of small-scale rituals among the Canela.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: "Among the Canella ceremonialism is of the utmost importance, absorbing a large part of the people's time and energy. At the same time it is so predominantly secular that to consider it as a part of religion would be doing violence to the facts" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:163).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: SCCS Variable 237 [note, equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 32: Jurisdictional Hierarchy] indicates that there are no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy (no political authority) beyond the local community (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Villages are led by a village chief (pa'hi) and a group of councilmen. "Chiefs exercise little political control and display a minimum of individual assertiveness, for the omnipresent ceremonial regulates most of the social life, and it is their and the council's duty to maintain the customary law rather than legislate anew. Chiefs lack badges of official status and receive not a whit more of the food offerings periodically presented in the plaza than the councilors associated with them. They work for a living precisely as any fellow tribesman. However, they do enjoy a measure of prestige, as shown by certain rules of etiquette" (Nimuendaju and Lowie, 1946:161).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that improved trails, for porters or animal carriers, are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that improved trails, for porters or animal carriers, are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall, 1972 (Column 10: Police), "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery."

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall, 1972 (Column 9: Judiciary), "supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community."

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Canela rely mainly on agriculture, with hunting as a secondary form of subsistence. Gathering and fishing supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Canela rely mainly on agriculture, with hunting as a secondary form of subsistence. Gathering and fishing supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas

(Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.